

THE ACTIVITY OF DEVELOPMENTAL CENTERS IN THE FORMATION OF CHILDREN'S ABILITIES

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Abstract. *The article examines the organization of development centers in preschool education based on a modern approach.*

Key words: *modern approach, focus, development, STEAM, critical thinking, independent thinking, active communication, individual order.*

Introduction

Preschool education is the first stage of the lifelong education system. Its main goal is to ensure the full development of the child's personality, the realization of his abilities, the formation of the skills necessary for reading, continuing education and preparing for successful schooling. The development of "State requirements for the development of younger and preschool age" and "First step" has created sample opportunities for the effective implementation of preschool education in the system of lifelong education. In the process of educational programs at school when organizing a developmental environment in an institution, it is important to take into account the age of characteristics and needs of children. At the same time content of creating an effective developing development includes:

- the content of the exhibitional - developments in the preschool educational institution should be in accordance with the cultural and historical values, national and regional traditions, nature and its educational climate.

- the content of the environment should form the basis of the primary worldview and contribute to the successful social adaptation of the child. It's true that, such innovations, aimed at updating the form and content of preschool education which require from all teachers, parents, and approach to raising a child readiness to learn in accordance with modern requirements. The Processes of development centers which organizes in groups in the preschool educational institutions, help children to constantly acquire and consolidate new knowledge. The main goal of development centers is to teach children to independently supplement knowledge, to adapt accordingly to the ongoing process of renewal.

Development centers for children include :

- adoption and implementation of changes;
- critical thinking;
- selection;
- be able to solve problems;
- to show creative thinking and inventive abilities;
- care for people, society, country, environment

Main part

Today's world is not as yesterday's, tomorrow will not be like today. Dynamic emerging technologies in all areas of human activity are being introduced. Modern children

occupy 65 percent of occupations exist today. Future technology experts, from various fields of science and engineering complex is in need of education and knowledge.

Today's world is not like yesterday's, and tomorrow will not be like today. Dynamically developing technologies are being introduced into all spheres of human activity. Sixty-five percent of modern children will engage in professions that do not exist today. Future professionals will require comprehensive training and knowledge from various fields of engineering, science and technology.

STEAM gives our children - a new generation of inventors, whose gives opportunity to research like scientists, capable in technology, design like engineers, be creative like artists and creating analytical thinking like a mathematician through. Nowadays, STEAM education is developing as one of the main global trends and is based on the integration of five areas into a single curriculum using a practical approach. The conditions for such education are its continuity and the development in children ability to interact in groups, in which they collect and exchange ideas. Therefore, the core curriculum includes modules for the development of logical thinking, such as Lego-technologies, children's research.

STEAM (S-science, T-technology, E-engineering, A- art , M-Mathematics) is a modern approach that combines science, technology, engineering, art and mathematics. The following important characteristics and skills will help the development of steam in children [2]:

- A comprehensive understanding of the problem;
- Creative thinking;
- Engineering approach;
- Critical thinking;
- Understanding and applying scientific methods;
- Understanding the basics of design.

Due to the STEAM approach, children will understand nature of the world and regularly explore it, thereby developing their interests, engineering style of thinking, the ability to overcome critical situations, teamwork and leadership skills, the foundations of self-expression, which, in turn, gives a radically new level of child development.

Building itself o- confidence . With this approach, each time they approach the goal, children create bridges and roads, airplanes and cars with their own hands. A “product” that does not give good results is repeatedly tested and improved. As a result, children feel that solving all problems on their own, achieving a goal, brings them inspiration, victory, adrenaline and joy, and each victory inspires more confidence in their abilities.

Active communication and teamwork. STEAM programs are also characterized by active communication and teamwork. During the discussion phase, they learn not to be afraid to comment. Often they don't sit around a table and test and develop “products” based on their designs. They would be always busy communicating in a team with educators and their friends that provides collaboration.

Develop an interest in technical sciences. The task of STEAM education in preschool and primary school age is to create the initial conditions for the development of interest. The basis for developing children's interest in the natural and technical sciences is to love what they do. STEAM is very effective and dynamic for kids in terms of preventing children from getting bored. They don't even notice that time is passing as well as they don't get tired. Their interest in

building rockets, cars, bridges, skyscrapers, electronic games, factories, logistics networks, submarines, science and technology would grow simultaneously.

Creative and innovative approaches to projects. STEAM training consists of six stages: question (task), discussion, design, build, test and improve. These steps are the foundation of a standard design approach. In turn, collaboration or sharing of different opportunities is the foundation of creativity. Thus, he can simultaneously apply science and technology in children and create new innovations. A well-organized, healthy social and spiritual environment encourages children to explore, be proactive and creative. At the same time, educators need to have a clear idea of how a child's development is going, and for this they need to constantly monitor them.

The educator delivers the learning material to the children in an appropriate manner, taking into account the age characteristics of the children. The role of the pedagogical team of preschool education institutions is to set appropriate goals, taking into account the interests, abilities and needs of each child, to support the natural interests of children, to develop in them the skills of joint development.

This approach will help solve life problems in children in the future. In many developed countries, including the USA, Japan, Israel, Singapore, Russia, this approach is effectively used in preschool education to develop creative and inventive skills in children.

Considering the specifics of a child's development, it is important to initially understand that all children go through certain stages of development and each child is unique and inimitable. In order to the teachers offered the children the same, similar things and activities, they should have a thorough understanding of their own unique distinctive indicators of development. Experts also emphasize that educators need to pay attention to differences in the abilities and interests of different children of the same age.

It refers to the types of activities that respond to children's interests in terms of the specifics of child development, that is, their level of mental, social and spiritual maturity. These activities are aimed at children's interest in nature, satisfaction with the experience and the desire to try their ideas in practice.

In the process of education in developmental centers, children themselves begin to voluntarily choose the appropriate developmental center. In the work of children in independent groups, individualization, the educator devises such activities that, although everyone is given the same instructions, each child is given the opportunity to succeed independently, based on it. The level of individualization can be optimized. By choosing the type of activity that requires dexterity and ingenuity, and by carefully observing the children, the educator can modify or adapt the assignments and materials as the need arises.

Based on the "First Step" curriculum, the following development centers will be created in preschool educational institutions:

- Construction and design center
- Role-playing and staging center
- Language and speech
- Center for Science and Nature
- Art center
- Center for Music and Rhythm

Development centers allow children to independently individualize the educational process, based on their personal skills and interests. For example, in an art center, one child cuts out a piece of paper and another one cuts a shape out of the paper with scissors. In the center of board games, one child sculpts a figure from four wooden cubes, while another prefers to sculpt a picture from twenty-five pieces of cardboard. The educator observes the children in the process and records ideas related to their development. Over time, he offers children materials that complicate the task or, depending on the situation, directly help the child to complete these tasks. As a result, the child can grow well.

Educators play the significant role of helping children in development centers, provide a wide range of classroom opportunities and plan activities so that each child can achieve an individual developmental level. The agenda should include various activities: in small groups, together and in collaboration with a mentor, individually or independently (time should be allocated for lessons of their choice, because children learn to make informed choices, to realize their interests and abilities). Children should be able to make their own choices, solve problems, work with others, set individual goals and know how to achieve them.

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